

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BOTON****FIRST NAME: YEMALIN LAMBERT****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

WRITING ACADEMIC PAPERS: FROM BASIC KNOWLEDGE TO EXPERT SKILLS

1)INTRODUCTION

As a language professional and having written so many assignments, course works, projects, and even final dissertations, I thought I had everything it takes to confidently proceed with my learning journey. Yet, little did I know that by embarking on this doctoral program with Euclid University, I now have to go back to high school. At least, that is what I thought when I read through the first two pages of the guidelines on basic tips for essay writing of the *EUCLID ACA - 401 Coursepack* for period one. However, I soon realize that the learning material, not only provides a flashback on the high school lessons of appropriate usage of punctuation, syntax and correct grammar, as well as sample corrections to previous papers, but it also discusses some PhD level elements such as rules of style and Latin abbreviations and expressions. Moreover, Prof. Cleenewerck's writing instructions video, in addition to its advice on various elements of style, also provides details about how EUCLID's students are expected to format and save assignment documents. Although short, simple, and very well-articulated, I must say that the video sounds to me like a strong warning that from now on, nothing will ever be like before, and that on this program, every detail counts.

I found the course material to be a robust and shrewdly designed didactic tool to quickly take the learner through what he/she should normally have learnt as foundational writing skills during his/her early years at school, and beef up these concepts with higher level and academic resources and tips. And, although a great deal of the notions discussed in the material are familiar to me, they have the merit of further consolidating and firming up my knowledge, and I therefore believe that I am starting the program on a good footing.

In this response paper, I will discuss several writing requirements that particularly caught my attention, notably the issue of plagiarism which I have a bitter past experience with. Thereafter the notion of punctuation, most especially the use of comma before conjunctions when listing items, then, the use of “me” and “I” as in “Bob and me” and “Bob and I.” The last element I will focus on is the Chicago (Turabian) Style and Usage in the CMS Crib Sheet by Dr. Abel Scribe PhD.

2) A FEW WRITING REQUIREMENTS FOR DISCUSSION

a) Plagiarism and my Personal Experience

Many sections from the beginning to end of the course material dealt with the issue of plagiarism. First, there is a whole slide show presentation which deals with plagiarism, qualifying it as “an important thing to avoid when writing papers”(EUCLID 2019, 5). Personally, I do not think I will ever lose sight of the extent to which plagiarism can be harmful, as it is done to the detriment of the author whose work and efforts have not been acknowledged, and for the offender, it makes one question their integrity and honesty whether this is perpetrated unconsciously or undertaken in bad faith.

In any case, there is a popular saying that goes: “if you ever get bitten by a snake, beware of worms.” I think I have learnt a good lesson with regard to plagiarism from my just completed MBA (Master of Business Administration) program. As a matter fact, I had to re-pay for and re-take my Marketing module all over again because in my final project for said module, there were instances where I did not know how to provide references for some of ideas I used for drafting my project because those were insights from materials that were translated into French and for which I did not have the necessary writers’ information. This was a bit naïve of me because I thought that hinging my work on those ideas was not a big deal and that no one would care about it, but I paid a high price; I lost twelve weeks’ efforts and time to plagiarism. Moreover, when writing my final dissertation for the program, I came across some very useful reviews of Matt Andrews’s book: *The Limits of Institutional Reform in Development: Changing Rules for Realistic Solutions*, and had to put them aside because although I had all the references on the author and his work, I did not know how to reference these works. The reason is that I could only have the dates of the reviews and names of the reviewers, whose works were excellent analyses which I could have exploited to further enrich my project. This therefore means that I am delighted and satisfied to find elements in these course materials on how to reference book reviews and translated materials.

Overall, plagiarism has been discussed in many parts of the material, which in my opinion, should be understood as a strong warning against something that is considered a serious academic offense with serious consequences (EUCLID 2019, 5)

b) Punctuation: Use of Comma before Conjunctions

When listing items, each item should be separated from the other by a comma; and to end the listing, a comma should be placed before the conjunction that adds the last item to the list. The reason for doing this is to avoid or reduce ambiguity and increase sentence effectiveness (EUCLID 2019, 20). For a non-native user of the English like me, this is a golden rule in that not only is it likely to disambiguate certain sentences, but it is also a demonstration of good writing capability and mastery of the rule. Further, it shows that when it comes to academic writing, every detail count.

Therefore, even though I may be at liberty to use or leave out the last comma, I best choose to include it, an option which is said to be formal language and also has the potential to decrease ambiguity and increase the effectiveness of a sentence (EUCLID 2019, 20).

c) The Use of “Bob and Me” and “Bob and I”

There are mistakes that some native speakers of English make and that may not be noticed by non-native speaker of English, because the latter naturally think that all native speakers do speak the best of the language and therefore repeat these mistakes. Besides, for a French speaker like me, this sounds so natural, as “Georges and me” is literally equivalent to “*George et moi*” which in French can serve as a subject for a verb. It takes careful attention to notice this confusion which I also used to make, especially when to use compound subjects. The material has reminded me that in English, an object pronoun cannot perform the action of a verb but can only receive the said action. It takes a pronoun or noun to perform the action of a verb (EUCLID 2019, 22). For instance, I used to say:

“A friend of mine and me attended the Union protest.”

“My family and me/myself were on vacation in London last year.”

From now on, I will make sure I pay more attention to this mistake and avoid it, especially when speaking orally, as I have noticed that now, the computer automatically underlines this mistake and suggests the “I” as a replacement for “me.”

d) The Chicago - Turabian Style and Usage in the CMS Crib Sheet by Dr. Abel Scribe PhD

This chapter of the material seemed a bit off-putting to me when I tried reading it for the first time. But later, I found it to be an amazing mine of wealth. The two elements that particularly caught my attention are how to hyphenate compound words and capitalization of geographical names.

i) Capitalization of Geographical Names

Place names that are used as official or officially recognized designations of those places should be considered as proper nouns and therefore treated as such by capitalizing them (EUCLID 2019, 45). Although this rule may require a bit of knowledge in geography and geopolitics, for a Diplomacy student, it is worth knowing to keep with protocol as appropriate in the area. This is quite important as I know how vehemently some of the dignitaries attending our functions or events react when the names of countries or organizations they represent are not properly written. For instance, being from West Africa and knowing that the name of my region means the part of the world where live the set of countries belonging to the ECOWAS (Economic Community of West African States) Community, I think I would naturally raise some eyebrows if West Africa is not capitalized; and I know ECOWAS authorities are strict about these details. I also remember that during one of the meetings of the Council of Ministers of ECOWAS, it was said that even the term community, when applied to ECOWAS, should always be capitalized to mean the ECOWAS Community.

ii) Hyphenating Compound Words

Although I can now differentiate between full-time compound words such as full-time itself, court-martial, which should be hyphenated when used as adjectives or nouns (EUCLID 2019, 46), I believe this rule is only easy to follow when dealing with compound words used as nouns. I find it difficult to distinguish between full-time compound words used as adjectives and those used as adverbs. Moreover, while searching for more understanding about this rule in the dictionary, I realized that the hyphen is dropped specifically for the compound words “full-time” when used as adverb or noun. On this particular issue, I will have to search further to better understand.

3) CONCLUSION

The course material, right from chapter one on Essay Writing to the Latin abbreviations and expressions as well as the video tutorials, is a useful tool not only to review the foundational writing rules that we often tend to forget, but it also helps anybody contemplating embarking on a serious learning journey to start on a clean sheet and refresh their knowledge and skills. And although I personally confess that it would be difficult for me to keep in mind all the detailed elements provided in it, I see this learning material to be something I should always keep on hand as a breviary for use all throughout this program and even the rest of my life.

REFERENCES

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